

ANALYSIS OF COTTON DRYING METHODS

Karshiev Bakhtiyor Eshkobilovich

Termez State University of Engineering and Agrotechnologies, associate professor

Abstract: *The article presents an analysis of convective, conductive, layer-by-layer drying of cotton, drying in infrared light, high frequency current and combined drying methods. The possibility of drying cotton with a layer in a stationary, boiling and suspended (fountain) state has been studied.*

Key words: *Cotton layer, mesh surface, hot air, stationary layer, hot air velocity, aerodynamic mode, channel formation rate, fountain formation rate.*

More than 10,000 types of materials are known to be dried. A large number of drying nozzles have been developed based on the characteristics of such materials, their properties, and the technological requirements for the drying process.

Foreign and local researchers have created various tips and tips for drying cotton, of which the following tips have been studied [1-3]:

- drying using a high voltage current;
- drying using infrared rays;
- layer drying;
- convective;
- conductive;
- combination tip.

During drying with the help of high-frequency current, it heats the wet material and evaporates the moisture due to the conversion of electrical energy into thermal energy.

Placed between the high-frequency oscillating circuit capacitor plates, the wet material heats up due to dielectric loss. As a result of the dielectric loss, the separation occurs as a result of the vibrational movement of the molecules of the material placed in the capacitor gap. Heat is collected throughout the entire volume of the material.

During the construction process, the temperature and humidity of the surface of the material and the temperature and humidity of the interior due to moisture evaporation will be proportional to the temperature and humidity of the interior. As a result, there are positive temperature and humidity differences that accelerate the exit of moisture from the inside to the surface.

Heating wet materials with the help of an electric current passing through dielectrics and semiconductors is extremely difficult, as long as there is an internal source of heat in the material.

The heating temperature is very high and the consumption of the drink is low. The use of high-voltage current in drying materials with a high contact surface and low thermal conductivity is recommended.

When drying with the help of infrared rays, the heat needed to evaporate moisture is provided by a radiant energy source.

In determining the drying temperature of wet materials with the help of infrared rays, it is necessary to determine the surface of the radiation energy generator, that is, the dimensions of internal radiation.

Optical radiation occurs as a result of electronic excitation of molecules and atoms of various radiating bodies, as well as vibrational and rotational movements of molecules and nuclei, and depends on the degree of blackness of the wet material. Quantitative measurement of radiation is called irradiance [4-6].

Because cotton is a porous, colloidal material, light penetrates into certain layers of it.

In radiation drying, the temperature gradient in the material is not high in the soft mode, and the mechanism of moisture movement inside the material is similar to convective drying.

In most cases, the temperature gradient is 20-50 °C/sm, as a result, at the beginning of the drying process, moisture moves from the surface to the interior, that is, from the cotton fiber to the seed cell, at the beginning of the drying process [7-9].

Under the influence of these factors, significant moisture differences appear in the fiber and between the fiber and the seed coat, that is, the surface of the fiber dries out, there is more moisture inside, as a result, the moisture release in the seed coat becomes slower because its temperature is lower than that of the fiber. Eca, temperature and moisture gradients are high in the seed coated with colloidal material, and the moisture is released slowly.

In many cases, the high radiant temperature causes the material to overheat, because the high temperature gradient is opposite to the moisture gradient, the movement of moisture from the inside to the surface of the material is slow.

These conditions limit the scope of application of the infrared drying tip for cotton. Because in this case, the surface of the fiber heats up quickly, the fiber dries quickly and causes excessive drying, the construction process is uneven, and the seed does not dry well. Convective drying is common in which hot air is used.

The kinetics of convective tip formation is highly dependent on the moisture and heat exchange between the warm air and the surface of the material, as well as the processes of moisture and heat movement within the material.

The most important factor in convective drying is the heating temperature of the material and the kinetics of its change, as well as the moisture gradients and movements on the surface of the material and inside it. Because the quality of the material being dried in many cases depends on its heating temperature, humidity and evenness of construction.

When cotton is dried, the fiber basically dries during the initial speed period, the temperature of which depends on the drying mode.

The drying mode can be hard or soft depending on the air temperature. In the soft mode, that is, when the air temperature is not high, the temperature of the fiber does not change almost and is equal to the wet temperature of the pichometer, and the vapor pressure on its surface is equal to the saturated vapor pressure at the wet bulb temperature.

In the hard drying mode, i.e. when the air temperature is high, the fiber temperature stop is switched off. As a result, the difference in temperature and humidity between fiber, seed coat and pith increases. Moisture is reduced more in the fiber than in the seed coat and pulp, resulting in a moisture gradient.

In order to ensure the uniformity of the construction process, it is necessary to accelerate the heating of the seed and to ensure that the moisture separation from the fiber and the seed is carried out in parallel, not in series.

In layer drying, moisture is released from cotton more quickly than in suspension drying.

Therefore, during layer drying, the air flow is filtered through the cotton layer, increasing the heat and moisture exchange surface, and increasing the air velocity at the surface of the seed and fiber.

This allows you to control the performance and moisture absorption over a wide range, taking into account the change in the cotton layer and drying time. However, despite the fact that the layer drying tip has a number of advantages, it was not used in production due to the uneven drying of cotton by the layer and the lack of development of the camera drying tip.

K.Sh.Shakirov, M.I.Ismoilov, B.E.Erofeeva, A.R.Suetin, A.R.Umarov and others worked on improving cotton drying in layers.

K.Sh.Shakirov studied the introduction of warm air from above during layer drying of cotton, and as a result, the optimal indicators of drying were determined: warm air temperature 120-130°C, speed 0.6-1 m/s, layer thickness 100 mm. But the recommended drying method was not applied to the production due to the unevenness of the construction layer by layer, insufficient productivity and drying speed.

M.I.Ismoilov, M.M.Niyazov, B.E.Erofeeva, A.R.Suetin in his research, the hydrodynamics of airing the cotton layer through the holes and the hydraulic resistance of the layer were studied, but no practical recommendations were developed [10-13].

The "Cotton Industry Research Center" studied the drying of cotton in layers, and recommended the optimal parameters of the drying process, air speed, and drying time (7-9 min). As a result of the study of internal moisture exchange in the cotton layer, an air distribution machine with a camera made in the form of a 100 mm diameter, 6 m long tube grid installed at an interval of 10 mm, cotton packing weight 30 kg/m², drying agent consumption 15000-17000 m³/hour, drying temperature 150-170°C was determined. But the maximum moisture content during the recommended drying cycle was 4-5,5%, which is certainly low. Increasing the moisture content only increased the build temperature, causing the fiber to overheat and dry out.

Studies studied the cycle mode of drying cotton in layers, in order to prevent overheating of the fiber, the "hot air-hot air-hot air" mode is used, the construction process continues even when hot air is supplied, and the possibility of using a high-temperature drying agent it was cleaned.

In this case, as a result of the decrease in the temperature of the fiber during the heating process, the temperature gradient $\Delta t_{sp} t_u - t_m$ between the fiber and the seed takes the opposite direction due to the fact that the temperature of the fiber is less than the temperature of the seed, as a result, it does not prevent the release of moisture from the seed, but accelerates it. It was recommended to dry cotton in layers in a cycle mode on a belt conveyor. But it was not put into practice because it could not provide the required productivity (10 t/h) and moisture extraction (10%). Further studies drying cotton in a layer in a simple and cyclic mode, it was found that the uniformity of moisture extraction from fiber and seed is good in the cyclic mode: hot and hot air supply times are 2030 seconds, hot air mechanical speed 0.48-0.7 kg/m²s, cooling air temperature from 20 to 50°C.

As a layer (at a certain height on the end of the mesh surface), convective (using air) and combined (simultaneously convective, conductive and layer drying) with cameras.

It should be noted that researchers have only studied drying of cotton in a stationary state by filtering warm air through it.

It is known that cotton can be in three states: stationary, boiling and suspended.

At the speed of hot air pact, the position and size of the cotton layer on the end of the mesh surface does not change, it remains motionless.

The increase in air speed causes the cotton layer to vibrate, and this vibration deepens, as a result, the cotton layer, its porosity and thickness increase, is in a state of boiling water. The air velocity at which the cotton layer begins to boil is called the critical boiling velocity $v_{кр}$. In this case, the passage of warm air through the cotton is smooth, the moisture separation is accelerated, and the further increase of the air speed causes the cotton layer to separate from the mesh surface and become suspended. The speed of air reaching this position is called the cotton lifting speed v_k . In this case, the cotton pieces are separated from each other, the height and size of the layer increases, and the cotton surface exposed to air increases.

The rate of drying cotton in a fluidized bed is much higher than drying in a stationary bed.

The experimenter of drying cotton in conductive and convective tips showed that it is possible to ensure uniform drying of fiber and seed by using them without cof.

It takes a certain amount of time for the cotton seed to dry, and as a result of continuous exposure of the inner air to the fiber, the temperature of the fiber increases, as a result, the fiber becomes excessively dry and its quality deteriorates. is several times higher than the air velocity during drying in a stationary bed. As a result of the up and down movement of the cotton pieces, the surface area of the cotton exposed to indoor air increases.

Cotton drying in the "boiling layer" is of scientific and practical importance. In the research in this direction, it is required to determine the mesh surface and its aerodynamic resistance, which ensures uniform boiling of cotton in the basically, determine the optimal thickness of the cotton layer, the limit of air speed change and the laws of their interaction with the moisture content of cotton, and develop a drying process in this basically.

REFERENCES:

1. Kamolovich, D. R., O'G'Li, A. N. U., Yusupovich, A. K., & Eshqobilovich, Q. B. (2024). TUKLI URUG'LIK CHIGITNI SARALASHNING TAKOMILLASHTIRILGAN TEXNOLOGIYASI. Механика и технология, 2(15), 169-175.
2. Абдихамидов, Н. У. Ў., Джамолов, Р. К., Каршиев, Б. Э., & Абдуллаев, К. Ю. (2024). ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ОСНОВНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ СОРТИРОВОЧНОГО АГРЕГАТА ВОЛОСАТЫХ СЕМЯН ХЛОПЧАТНИКА МЕТОДОМ МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОГО ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ. Universum: технические науки, 4(5 (122)), 39-44.
3. Эшқобилович, Қ. Б. (2023). ПАХТАНИ ҚУРИТИШ ЖАРАЁНИНИ ТОЛА ВА ЧИГИТ НАМЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ. Механика и технология, (2 (5) Спецвыпуск), 309-315.
4. Eshqobilovich, Qarshiev Baxtiyor, Gulboev Otabek Abdimurod O'G'Li, and Narzullaev Fazliddin Shuhrat O'G'Li. "QURITILGAN PAHTANI PNEVMATIK UZATISHDA TOLA VA CHIGIT TEMPERATURALARIGA TA'SIRINI TAHLILI." Механика и технология 1 (8) Спецвыпуск (2024): 226-230.

5. Абдихамидов Н.У., Джамолов Р.К., Қаршиев Б.Э., Абдуллаев К.Ю. Саралаш камерага ўрнатилган чигитни доналовчи тароқ мосламасининг параметрларини аниқлаш. *Фан ва технологиялар тараққиёти илмий – техникавий журнал.* №1/2024, Бухоро-2024й-2856.

6. Қаршиев БЭ П. А. П., Сайидова М. Ҳ. Пахтани қатламда қуритишнинг аэродинамик режимларини аниқлаш тадқиқоти // *Фан ва технологиялар тараққиёти. Илмий-техникавий ва амалий журнал.* Бухоро. ISSN. – С. 2181-8193.

7. Parpiyev A. P. et al. Tozalash jarayonida arrali seksiyalardan ajralib chiqqan chiqindi ulushlarini baholash natijalari taxlili // *O‘zbekiston to‘qimachilik jurnali.* ISSN. – 2010. – Т. 6262. – №. 1. – С. 2022.

8. Каршиев Б. Э., Исмаатов С. С. РАВНОМЕРНОСТЬ СУШКИ КОМПОНЕНТОВ ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА // *Экономика и социум.* – 2023. – №. 9 (112). – С. 485-489.

9. Парпиев А. П., Каршиев Б. Э. РАВНОМЕРНОСТЬ СУШКИ КОМПОНЕНТОВ ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА // *Universum: технические науки.* – 2022. – №. 9-2 (102). – С. 51-54.

10. Каршиев Б. Э. и др. Пахтани тозалашга тайёрлаш технологиясининг таҳлили // *RESULTS OF NATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH.* – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6.

11. Каршиев Б.Э., Парпиев А.П., Хушбаков А.Н. Анализ температуры, влажности волокна и семян в технологических процессах на хлопкоочистительных предприятиях // *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE: YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 2022 Prague, Czech.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7117865>.

12. Қаршиев БЭ П. А. П. Пахта ва уни компонентларини қатламда қуритиш тадқиқоти // *ЎзМУ хабарлари. Илмий журнал.* ISSN. – С. 2181-7324.

13. Қаршиев БЭ П. А. П., Сайидова М. Ҳ. Пахтани қатламда қуритишнинг аэродинамик режимларини аниқлаш тадқиқоти // *Фан ва технологиялар тараққиёти. Илмий-техникавий ва амалий журнал.* Бухоро. ISSN. – С. 2181-8193.